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SUSTAINABLE SUPPORT SYSTEMS IN THE HOTEL INDUSTRY: A MULTILEVEL STUDY FROM TURKEY

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Abstract: This study tests the cross-level association between green organizational support (GOS) among team members, green team resilience (GTR), green work engagement (GWE), and pro-environmental behaviour (PEB). Data for this study came from 59 work groups and 372 individuals working in 14 hotels in Antalya, Türkiye. To account for the nested data structure, hierarchical linear modeling was employed using R programming language. The present research reveals that GOS directly and indirectly correlates with GTR, GWE, and PEB. In addition, GOS promotes GTR and fosters GWE and PEB. The authors infer that eco-friendly support provided by the organization to the hotel employees can facilitate the green resilience of teams and boost employees' GWE, consequently increasing individual-level PEB. Practitioners can utilize these insights to implement effective strategies that support environmental initiatives, improve team dynamics, and engage employees in sustainability efforts, thereby contributing to the overall environmental performance of hotels.

Keywords: Green organizational support; green team resilience; work engagement; hotel industry; Antalya.

1. Introduction

In a highly competitive market marked by ongoing worldwide degradation due to pollution, manufacturing toxins, and waste, managers are increasingly recognizing the necessity of environmental conservation as well as adopting eco-friendly initiatives (Knezevic Cvelbar et al., 2024; Olorunsola et al., 2024). This awareness has led tourism organizations to prioritize environmental sustainability (Conefrey & Hanrahan, 2024; Qin & Hsu, 2022; Zhang et al., 2024). Employees in the tourism sector are viewed as vital ambassadors who prioritize their institutions' environmental commitments and enhance the firm's sustainability (Kalyar et al., 2021). In addition, the general public holds the view that companies are responsible for minimizing their environmental impact and contributing

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to global sustainability efforts. Although the specifics of this responsibility are still debated, global industry leaders agree that businesses play a vital role in achieving sustainability (Manosuthi et al., 2024). Rather than solely focusing on external stakeholders, many organizations have introduced initiatives to encourage their employees to adopt eco-friendly behaviors in the workplace. These pro-environmental actions, known as employees' green practices, align with a company's commitment to social and environmental responsibility. Moreover, engaging in environmentally friendly activities at work is seen as a moral duty for employees (Qin & Hsu, 2022; Zhang et al., 2024). In a highly competitive industry, tourism managers recognize that concentrating on ecological sustainability and fostering eco-friendly employee behaviour is crucial evidence of the company's commitment to sustainability (Zhao & Zhou, 2021). The cornerstone of the organization's environmental support is the employees' impressions of eco-friendly actions (Aboramadan & Karatepe, 2021). Green organizational support (GOS) is "...the particular beliefs maintained by individuals on how much their efforts to eco-friendly practices are valued by the firm" (Lamm et al., 2015, p. 209) and results in environmentally-friendly job outcomes such as green innovative work behavior (Aboramadan et al., 2022) and green creativity (Hameed et al., 2022). Despite this knowledge, tourism literature lacks evidence of the positive and non-effects GOS might have on hotel employees (Aboramadan et al., 2022). This is unfortunate since management cannot fulfil the organization's environmental sustainability objectives without employee participation (Karatepe et al., 2022). Green organizational support (GOS), green team resilience (GTR), green work engagement (GWE), and pro-environmental behavior (PEB) are important components in advancing sustainability within organizations. Çop et al. (2021) defined GTR as "the capacity to recover from environmental-related struggles, catastrophe, difficulties, or any form of risk to the team" (P. 673). Prior research has established that GOS can significantly influence employees' environmental attitudes and behaviors (Lamm et al., 2015). GWE is described as "the energy an employee puts in his green work-related tasks, the willingness to exert efforts at the green level, and the absorption level in green work" (Aboramadan, 2022, p.10). Studies have also shown that GTR and GWE contribute to employees' capacity to cope with environmental challenges and enhance their commitment to green practices (Çop et al., 2021). Pro environmental behavior at the individual level is vital for the overall sustainability goals of an organization. On the other hand, PEB is explained as "any action taken by employees that she or he thought would improve the environmental performance of the company" (Ramus & Steger, 2000, p. 606). PEB in the workplace offer numerous advantages, not only for organizations but also for society at large. They contribute to alleviating severe environmental challenges, benefit everyone, and are strategically beneficial for businesses. In fact, PEBs are increasingly recognized as a critical factor in determining an organization's overall success in the 21st century (Zhang et al., 2024). Despite the established importance of these concepts, there is limited understanding of how these elements interact at the team and individual levels within the tourism and hospitality industry. Specifically, the cross-level associations between GOS, GTR, GWE, and PEB remain underexplored. Furthermore, there is a need to understand how GOS can indirectly influence PEB through GTR and GWE. Addressing these gaps is essential to developing more effective strategies for promoting sustainability in hotels. Hence, our study aims to test the cross-level association between GOSN among team members, GTR,

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GWE, and PEB. This paper adds to the literature on tourism and hospitality (T&H) in the following ways. First, most empirical research on environmental management has focused on organizations' environmental sustainability initiatives or the viewpoints of consumers/directors (e.g., Assaker et al., 2020). There is a scant study on the green behavior of tourism employees. For instance, a recent meta-analysis of pro environmental behavior (PEB)-related articles by Loureiro et al. (2022) suggests that employee involvement concerning "pro-environmental behavior" (p. 14) must be investigated. Second, the available literature is bereft of evidence appertaining to intervening mechanisms linking the influence of green organizational support on employee green job outcomes among T&H employees (Aldabbas et al., 2020; Karatepe et al., 2022; Olorunsola et al., 2024). Relevant literature reveals sparse research about the underlying process through which green organizational support (GOS) is associated with hotel employees' pro-environmental behaviour (PEB). The research mentioned above lacuna is evident in a relevant meta-analytic (Ifikhar et al., 2021) and systematic review (Hall et al., 2023) research on team resilience have not found any support for the link between GOS and PEB through the intervening role of (green team resilience) GTR. Given the research void mentioned above, this study contributes to the literature by treating GTR as an intervening variable in the link between GOS and hotel employees' PEB. Third, empirical studies report that green organizational support (GOS) boosts employees' eco-friendly job outcomes (Aboramadan & Karatepe, 2021). However, it is mysterious whether green work engagement (GWE) plays a mediating role in the relationship between job resources (GOS) and green job outcomes. This gap has been underscored in several recent pieces (Aboramadan et al., 2022; Çop et al., 2021; Karatepe et al., 2022). Additionally, current findings have started to relate GOS to many job outcomes (Hameed et al., 2022). In addition, this is the first multilevel study to investigate GWE as the intervening variable of the effect of GOS on hotel employees' PEB. Such gaps are evident in current GOS-related publications (Hameed et al., 2022; Karatepe et al., 2022). By examining such relationships, it would be possible to determine whether GOS boosts employees' PEB due to GWE. Lastly, utilizing a methodically chosen sample of 48 articles, Tanova and Bayighomog's (2022) study revealed that the most eco-friendly human resource management-related research was individual-level, which is also valid for GOS research (Aboramadan & Karatepe, 2021; Hameed et al., 2022). Accordingly, recent pieces called for studies to conduct multilevel approaches to GOS (Aboramadan et al., 2021). This research gap was also identified in a study by Ari et al. (2020), who believed multilevel research would contribute to advancing research on the relationship between eco-friendly social support (GOS) and its outcomes. In response to the research mentioned above calls and research lacunas, this work contributes to the literature by offering a multilevel model. It experimentally examines the influence of GOS among team members on GTR, GWE, and PEB.

Literature review and hypothesis development

2.1 Green organizational support and green team resilience

The Broaden-and-Build Theory, developed by Fredrickson (2001), supports the hypothesis that green organizational support (GOS) positively relates to employees' green team resilience (GTR) by explaining how positive emotions can enhance individuals' adaptive capacities. When organizations provide strong support for

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environmental initiatives, employees experience positive emotions such as pride and satisfaction. These emotions broaden their cognitive and behavioral repertoires, encouraging innovative thinking and collaborative problem-solving (Lin et al., 2016). Over time, this broadening effect helps build enduring personal and social resources, such as enhanced problem-solving skills and stronger social networks, which are crucial for resilience (Çop et al., 2021). Thus, GOS fosters a positive emotional climate and equips employees with the resources needed to effectively navigate and overcome environmental-related problems, triggering greater GTR. In addition, social exchange theory (SET) is a psychological tenet that elucidates social behaviour regarding the exchange of resources between individuals and groups. Proposed by Cropanzano and Mitchell (2005), SET posits that associations are formed and maintained akin to the reciprocal exchange of resources, such as support, trust, and rewards. The theory suggests that individuals engage in social interactions and relationships that they perceive to be beneficial, where the benefits outweigh the costs (Valle et al., 2019). This reciprocal exchange fosters trust, loyalty, and a sense of obligation, leading to stronger, more cooperative relationships over time (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005). Employees who feel that their workplace appreciates as well as reward their endeavours at the workplace feel a responsibility to assist the organization in accomplishing its objectives (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002). This is because perceived organizational support, which includes care, approval, and respect, enhances employee performance (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002). In our study, we focus on green organizational support (GOS). Aboramadan et al. (2021) described GOS as employees' perceptions of how much their organizations care for and value their environmental and green contributions (p.1792). Generally, when employees sense that their environmental efforts are recognized and valued by the organization, they are likely to exhibit thorough performance also engage in discretionary behaviours. Employees feel supported in a workplace that appreciates and values their environmental contributions and accomplishments (Aboramadan & Karatepe, 2021). When organizations demonstrate their environmental commitment and efforts to their employees by offering explicit green activities, green help, and eco-friendly development supervision, employees are expected to reciprocate by exhibiting green behaviours. In addition, by applying SET, when organizations invest in GOS by providing resources, training, and recognition for environmental efforts, employees are likely to respond positively by developing stronger team cohesion and resilience. Green team resilience (GTR) is defined as the power to recuperate from environmental-related problems, disasters, or any form of danger to the team (Çop et al., 2021, p.673). Sommer et al. (2016) underlined that interaction among employees is one of the essential factors in constructing a team's capacity to react effectively to environmental problems. Individuals on a team are more likely to be resilient if they get social support from their organization or supervisor. Akin to the information described above, Çop et al. (2021) found that ecofriendly leader support boosts the GTR and GWE of employees working in Turkish hotels. Based on the aforementioned discussion, our research proposes the following hypothesis:

H1a. Green organizational support positively relates to employees' green team resilience.

2.2 Green organizational support and green work engagement

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Social Exchange Theory (SET) provides a captivating framework for understanding the link between green organizational support (GOS) and green work engagement (GWE). According to SET, social behavior is driven by the exchange of resources, where individuals engage in relationships that they perceive to be rewarding (Cropanzano and Mitchell, 2005). Based on the SET, when employees receive valuable resources from their workplace, they feel a sense of obligation to reciprocate. In the context of GOS, if followers feel that their workplace genuinely values and supports their environmental endeavors, they will show a proclivity to respond with elevated levels of engagement toward ecofriendly practices. There is some evidence that organizational support exerts a direct impact on work engagement. For example, Karatepe and Aga (2016) found a positive link between organizational support and work engagement among bank employees. Similarly, Shi and Gordon (2021) found that organizational support was positively linked with work engagement. Karatepe et al. (2022) found that management commitment to the ecological environment positively affects hotel employees' GWE in Ankara, Türkiye. Bhutto et al. (2021) revealed a positive relationship between green inclusive leadership (social support) and GWE in tourism and hospitality sector. However, little attention is paid to green organizational support (GOS) – green work engagement (GWE) link. GWE is characterized by the energy an employee invests in environmentally-focused responsibilities, their inclination to put forth effort towards ecofriendly practices, as well as his/her level of absorption in green work (Aboramadan, 2022, p.10). Exceptional research by Karatepe et al. (2022) found that perceived organizational support for the environment positively related to work engagement among hotel employees. Another research by Aboramadan and Karatepe (2022) found that GOS affects organizational citizenship behavior toward the organization among hotel employees. However, to the best of the authors' knowledge, there is no empirical study about the relationship between GOS and GWE in hotel employees. Broadly speaking, our research focuses on GWE in the milieu of GOS is both innovative and necessary as it addresses a critical gap in the literature. While existing research has primarily concentrated on the impact of organizational support on general employee engagement and performance, the nuanced relationship between GOS and GWE—especially within the unique cultural and operational setting of Türkiye's hotel industry—has received limited attention. By gauging how GOS impacts employees' intrinsic motivation to engage in environmentally sustainable practices, this study not only extends our knowledge of the mechanisms driving GWE but also extends current research by adding empirical evidence from a multilevel perspective. This approach offers new insights into how GOS can be strategically leveraged to foster a more sustainable workforce, thereby contributing to the broader discourse on organizational sustainability and employee well-being. Hence, we posit that:

H1b. Green organizational support positively relates to employees' green work engagement.

2.3 Green organizational support and employees' pro-environmental behaviors

Organizational support has long been recognized as a crucial socio-emotional resource that influences employee behavior. According to social exchange theory, when employees perceive that their socio emotional needs are being met by the organization, they are likely to reciprocate positively, in alignment with the norm of reciprocity (Aboramadan et al., 2021; Valle et al., 2019). This principle of reciprocity is particularly relevant in the context

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of green organizational support (GOS), where employees perceive that their organization is genuinely committed to environmental sustainability. In return, employees feel a sense of obligation to reciprocate by engaging in pro-environmental behaviors (PEB) that benefit both the organization and the environment. For instance, when employees observe that their organization invests in green practices, such as reducing waste or promoting energy efficiency, they are more likely to adopt similar behaviors in their daily work routines. Empirical studies have shown that employees who perceive high levels of organizational support are more inclined to go beyond their formal job responsibilities, engaging in discretionary behaviors that align with the organization's values and goals (Chiang & Hsieh, 2012). In the case of GOS, this may manifest as employees actively participating in sustainability initiatives, such as recycling programs, energy-saving efforts, or advocating for environmental policies within the workplace. By integrating the principle of reciprocity with GOS, this study highlights the critical role that perceived organizational support plays in fostering PEB, thereby extending the application of social exchange theory to the domain of environmental sustainability. Specifically, when employees feel that their valuable contributions are highly regarded by their organization, they reciprocate by exhibiting positive behaviors such as commitment (Cheng et al., 2016) and organizational citizenship behavior (Chiang & Hsieh, 2012). For example, Aboramadan and Karatepe (2021) found that GOS positively affects job performance and citizenship behavior toward the organization among hotel employees. Another research by Olorunsola et al. (2024) found that GOS positively affects green task performance. In line with the aforementioned discussions, employees who feel their environmental efforts are recognized and valued by their organization will cultivate higher levels of GOS. Consequently, this appreciation motivates them to reciprocate through green outcomes, including pro-environmental behavior. Therefore, we hypothesize the following:

H1c. Green organizational support positively relates to employees' pro-environmental behaviors.

2.4 Green work engagement and pro-environmental behavior

Schaufeli (2002, p. 74) defined work engagement as "a favourable, rewarding, work-related cognitive process marked by vigour, dedication, and absorption." This research specifically concentrated on the notion of "green work engagement," which has been characterized by Aboramadan (2022) as "the amount of effort that employee invests in eco-friendly practices, the desire to utilize actions at the green level, and the level of engagement in green work." (p. 10). According to the social exchange theory, individuals with elevated levels of engagement are more likely to maintain a stable and healthy interaction with his/her employers. This, in turn, generates positive employment-related outcomes (Saks, 2006). Consequently, such signs will motivate employees to perform their duties and enable them to engage in extracurricular activities. For example, an earlier study (Arasli et al., 2020) indicates that job engagement is a powerful determinant of work performance and extra-role activities. A novel piece found that engaged employees exhibit low levels of non-green behaviours due to positive mutual interaction. These individuals are less likely to utilize or consume scarce resources in an unsustainable manner (Karatepe et al., 2020). Arasli et al. (2020) found that highly engaged hotel employees display environmental commitment in their recent work. In addition, Bailey et al. (2017) meta-analytic research demonstrated the relationship between employee engagement, task performance, and extra-role performance. Another research done by Aboramadan

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(2022) found positive link between green work engagement and employee green behaviours in higher education. Karatepe et al. (2022) reported that green work engagement positively affected task-related pro-environmental behaviour among hotel employees. Akin to the initial findings, this study hypothesizes that enthusiastic workers who are proud of their jobs and focused on their tasks can contribute to the workplace by engaging in proenvironmental activities (Karatepe et al., 2020). Even though eco-friendly behaviours can be considered extra work, highly engaged staff are more inclined to exert pro-environmental behaviours because they find their work captivating and valuable, devote their full attention to work-related tasks, and prioritize environmental sustainability. Hence the following hypothesis was surmised:

H2. Green work engagement is positively related to employees' pro-environmental behavior.

2.5 Green team resilience and employees' pro-environmental behavior

Team resilience is "the ability to recover from failure, losses, disputes, or any other danger to their wellness" (West et al., 2009, p. 253). Çop et al. (2021) have defined green team resilience as "the ability to rebound from ecological problems, calamities, obstacles, or any type of risk to the team" (p. 673). Although the significance of such preceding meta-analyses and reviews on resilience, important topics still need to be addressed. Prior literature review and recent research underlined that team-level resilience is partially investigated (Çop et al., 2021; Hartmann et al., 2020). This is regrettable, considering that researchers have emphasized the importance of understanding team resilience and have begun to experimentally study the effects of team resilience (Meneghel et al., 2016). The notion of resilience has been predominantly used in organization and management as the capacity to effectively respond to adversity, which can emerge from either substantial disruption or the accumulation of countless little interferences (Sutcliffe & Vogus, 2003). This study expanded on the prior team resilience research and highlighted its effects. Similar to the individualistic performance method, research suggests that team-performing individuals tend to exhibit a certain degree of behavioral consistency (Guchait et al., 2016). Providing an insightful grasp of the idea, Totterdell (2000) found that team members who demonstrate the same degree of green team resilience may react similarly to mutual happenings and subsequently react psychologically in the context of this study. Meneghel et al. (2016) revealed that team resilience affects productivity and performance within the workplace. Therefore, this research focused on green team resilience. Green team resilience plays a crucial role in shaping individual pro-environmental behaviour within organizations, particularly in high-stress environments like the hospitality industry. Green team resilience reflects a team's collective capacity to adapt, recover, and grow stronger when facing environmental challenges. This resilience fosters a supportive environment that encourages a culture of shared responsibility, where members feel more confident and motivated to engage in eco-friendly behaviours (Çop et al., 2021). For instance, a resilient team might collaboratively develop innovative solutions to reduce waste or improve energy efficiency, inspiring individual members to adopt similar practices. Empirical evidence suggests that resilient teams are more effective in overcoming obstacles (Çop et al., 2021) and sustaining pro-environmental initiatives, thereby increasing the likelihood of individual pro-environmental behaviour. Although previous research has emphasized individual

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resilience (Hartmann et al., 2020), the role of team-level resilience in driving pro-environmental behaviour remains underexplored (Hall et al., 2023). By focusing on how green team resilience influences pro-environmental behaviour, this study fills that gap and offers new insights into the team dynamics that promote sustainability within organizations. Based on the above arguments, the following hypothesis is established:

H3. Green team resilience is positively related to employees' pro-environmental behaviour.

2.6 Green team resilience as a mediator

The job demands-resources (JD-R) theory's psychological route facilitates the development of the green organizational support- green team resilience - pro-environmental behaviour link. In the workplace, supportive leaders celebrate and promote workers' knowledge, development, and growth (Meneghel et al., 2016) which sends strong signals to staff that their work objectives are reachable.

The hotel's workforce that receives enough assistance is more resilient as a team and thus produces better results in the workplace. Akin to the theory above, personal resources can be similar to job resources, favourably affecting green team resilience. Because of the availability of mutually beneficial connections, resilient hotel personnel are much more inclined to take part in eco-friendly practices (Çop et al., 2021). Prior studies have not addressed resilience at the team-level analysis (Hartmann et al., 2020). This is unfortunate since researchers have underlined the need for understanding resilience at the team level (Hartwig et al., 2020; King et al., 2016; Hartmann et al., 2020) and have started to empirically investigate the drivers and consequences of team resilience (Peñarroja et al., 2022). In addition, several studies gauged team resilience. West et al. (2009) showed a correlation between team resilience and team cohesiveness and collaboration. Fan et al. (2021) discovered that team resilience is positively associated with team innovation and effectiveness. Meneghel et al. (2016) reported that team resilience entirely mediated the benefits of good collective emotions on in-role and extra-role teams. Constructing on the functional perspective of organizational support (e.g., Karatepe et al., 2022; Zhao & Huang, 2022), it is examined that green team resilience is a mediating variable through which green organizational support may positively affect employees' pro-environmental behaviour. Consequently, when an organization provides strong support for environmental initiatives, it fosters a collective sense of purpose and commitment within teams (Olorunsola et al., 2024). This supportive environment enhances the team's resilience, enabling them to effectively adapt to and overcome environmental challenges. As teams become more resilient, they create a culture of shared responsibility and mutual encouragement, which, in turn, motivates individual team members to engage in pro-environmental behaviours. Essentially, green team resilience mediates serves as the bridge that connects the organizational-level support with individual-level behaviours, ensuring that the benefits of GOS are fully realized in the form of increased pro-environmental behaviour among employees. Based on the information provided above, the next hypotheses is articulated:

H4. Green team resilience mediates the relationship between green organizational support and perceived pro-environmental behavior.

2.7 Green work engagement as a mediator

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Generally, work engagement was revealed to be a substantial mediator in several studies (Aboramadan, 2022; Ibrahim et al., 2019; Karatepe et al., 2019). Work engagement is commonly perceived as a motivator to influence performance outcomes (Shi et al., 2021; Wijayati et al., 2022). Social exchange theory SET is used to compose the green organizational support – green work engagement – pro-environmental behaviour (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005). The “Organizational support theory” proclaims that followers who think his/her efforts are being noticed and praised by the organization feel they have to assist the organization achieve its objectives (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002). This is because employees do better when they think their manager cares, approves of them, and respects those (Nazir et al., 2018). When employees believe their contributions to the environment are acknowledged and appreciated by the workplace, they are more inclined to work diligently and complete tasks independently. If the company values its environmental contributions and accomplishments, employees feel like they are being cared for (Aboramadan & Karatepe, 2021). In this situation, they would do their jobs well and act in good ways for the environment. JD-R theory's motivational pathway suggests that job resources increase employees' GWE, resulting in favorable work-related outcomes (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017). The path GOS → GWE → employee outcomes has also been confirmed by a recent piece (Karatepe et al., 2022). Similarly, GOS treated as an ideal eco-friendly resource, leading to GWE among hotel staff. Considering the principle of exchange (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005), those who demonstrate high levels of green work engagement as a result of green organizational support are more inclined to exhibit pro-environmental behaviour. Aboramadan's (2022) research showed that GWE was a significant variable regarding the link between green human resource practices and green job outcomes. Karatepe et al. (2022) study showed that green work engagement mediated the link between management's commitment and eco-friendly job outcomes. Another study found that green servant leadership and employees' workplace green behaviour link is mediated by green work engagement (Mughal et al., 2024). Abdou et al. (2023) found that the effect of green transformational leadership on employees' environmental performance is mediated by green work engagement. Based on the aforementioned information and findings, the following hypotheses will be tested:

H5. Green work engagement mediates the link between green organizational support and perceived pro environmental behavior.

Below, a conceptual model of the paper can be seen (Figure 1).

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Figure 1. Conceptual Model

Methods

3.1 Sampling and procedure

The current sample consists of employees from Antalya and Türkiye five-star hotels. Türkiye is one of the top 10 tourist destinations, receiving forty percent of all international arrivals (UNWTO, 2019). Antalya is one of the country's most popular tourist destinations (Karatepe et al., 2021). According to data received from the "Antalya Provincial Directorate of Culture and Tourism," there were 541 four- and five-star hotels at the time of the research (Arasli et al., 2019). Due to the sample's limitation to the front-line staff at hotels, the empirical research presented in the literature have utilized the approach of purposive sampling (Ozturk et al., 2021). Purposive sampling was employed to ensure the selection of participants who were most relevant to the study's objectives. This method allowed us to specifically target employees directly involved in service delivery. There are at least three selection criteria for these hotel kinds and frontline workers. Initially, five-star hotels devote considerable attention to environmental responsibility and long-term care (Karatepe et al., 2022). Second, frontline employees are at the centre of the process when it comes to offering the hotel's services to customers and providing value to achieve customer happiness and cultivate customer loyalty (Jung et al., 2021). Thirdly, hotel management can only achieve environmental sustainability objectives with its workers. The management of 14 out of 22 five-star hotels consented to participate. Data for this study were gathered from service employees in five five-star hotels in Antalya. The sample included employees in the front-of-the-house and back-of-the-house sections of the hotels, including primarily food and beverage, housekeeping, front office, and concierge services. The majority of the employees working in the hotels were Turkish. Hence, only Turkish employees were surveyed in this study. The research utilized a back-translation technique along with an expert review to enhance the questionnaire's content validity and ensure linguistic consistency (McGorry, 2000). Initially in English, the scales underwent translation

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into Turkish by a team with expertise in tourism management. Subsequently, a bilingual scholar performed the back-translation from Turkish to English. The comparison between the back-translated version and the original confirmed their equivalence (Zhou et al., 2022). A preliminary pilot test with 15 respondents confirmed that the survey's wording, measurement, and item order were accurate. For this study, 600 potential respondents were contacted, and each received a sealed envelope containing the research aims and the questionnaire. One of the authors of this study managed the distribution and collection of the questionnaires. Hotel management assigned an HR staff member to assist with the data collection process. A total of 390 responses were returned, and after excluding 11 surveys with incorrect responses and 7 with incomplete data, 372 valid responses were obtained from 59 work groups.

Table 1. Profile of the Participants

Demographic	Category	Number	Percentage
Gender	Male	231	62.1%
	Female	141	37.9%
Age Group	18-24	156	40%
	25-34	129	33%
	Other (35+)	105	27%
Education Level	High School or Less	188	48%
	Bachelor's Degree	83	21.2%
	Higher Degree	66	17%
	Other	53	13.8%
Work Experience	Less than 1 year	126	34%
	1-3 years	158	42.5%
	More than 3 years	106	27.5%
Department	Food and Beverage	195	50%
	Housekeeping	69	17.7%
	Front Desk	31	8.1%
	Other	95	24.2%

Work group refers to a team of employees within the hotel who collaborate regularly and share common tasks or objectives. These groups function as units within departments such as housekeeping, front desk, food and beverage, maintenance, or management. The sealed envelopes were collected from HR clerks once the data collection was completed. The response rate for the sample was 65%. The minimum and maximum group sizes were three and fifteen respondents, respectively, with an average of 6.3% per work group. The characteristics of the participants are illustrated in Table 1.

3.2 Instrument

Group-level: Questions utilized to gauge GOS were adapted from Karasek et al. (1982). Example items include (a) "My organization makes an active effort to help employees be environmentally proactive." All modified items

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were evaluated on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree; 5 = strongly agree). GOS individual scores were aggregated to the group level in this study. The intraclass correlations (ICC) and inter-rater agreement ($r_{wg[j]}$) provided the statistical justification for the aggregation. The $r_{wg[j]}$ was 0.82, indicating strong within-group agreement (0.71–0.90) (LeBreton & Senter, 2008). Moreover, the $ICC_{[1]} = 0.76$ and $ICC_{[2]} = 0.95$ evidenced inter-rater reliability (LeBreton & Senter, 2008), while ANOVA results suggested group-level GOS mean scores were significantly different: $F(58, 313) = 22.37, p < 0.001$. The 7-item GTR scale was adopted from Mallak's (1998) work and was also used in a study by Çop et al. (2021). The results supported the group-level aggregation: $r_{wg[j]} = 0.69, ICC_{[1]} = 0.29$ and $ICC_{[2]} = 0.72, F(58, 313) = 2.97, p < 0.001$. Employee-level: GWE was measured using a scale adapted from Schaufeli et al. (2006). As this scale was initially established to gauge work engagement, the six questions were adapted to gauge green employee engagement (Aboramadan, 2022). An example item for this scale is: "Since my organization is environmentally friendly, I am proud of my work." PEB was measured using four items and adopted from the research by Afsar et al. (2016) and Peng et al. (2020).

3.3 Analytic strategy

This research model presents a two-level design: employees (individual level, Level 1) clustered within work groups (group level, Level 2). To account for the nested data structure, hierarchical linear modeling (HLM) was employed using R programming language (R Core Team, 2021) and the lme4 package (Bates et al., 2015). Consistent with recent recommendations (e.g., González-Romá & Hernández, 2022), the restricted maximum likelihood (REML) with Kenward-Roger correction was applied to fit the estimated models to test the direct relationships hypotheses. This method was preferred to multilevel structural equation modeling, which is recommended for large samples (at least 100 L2 units) (González-Romá & Hernández, 2022). Lastly, a Monte Carlo-based 95% confidence interval (CI_{MC}) with 20,000 resamples was implemented to statistically test the significance of the proposed indirect effects (Preacher et al., 2010; Preacher & Selig, 2012). CI_{MC} , compared to other bootstrap procedures (e.g., bias-corrected accelerated bootstrap), performs better CI calibration and control of Type I error. The CIs that did not straddle zero indicated statistically significant indirect effects. In addition, the estimated parameters' effect sizes with η^2 and intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) for the analysis of variance and multilevel frameworks (Preacher & Kelley, 2011) and v^2 for the indirect effects reported (Gaskin et al., 2023). An ICC value indicates the proportion of variance attributed to differences between groups (i.e., group influence) relative to the total variance (i.e., overall influence). A value exceeding 0.1 suggests a substantial group influence that warrants consideration (Cho et al., 2020). The η^2 values indicate the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that is accounted for by the independent variables while v^2 values for indirect effects help elucidate the magnitude of mediation effects, offering insights into the practical significance of the pathways through which green organizational support influences green team resilience, green work engagement, and pro environmental behavior.

3.4 Common method variance treatment and test

Several procedural protocols and statistical controls were implemented to address the possibility of CMV (Podsakoff et al., 2003). First, the survey's cover page included the following information: "Your hotel's

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administration strongly encourages cooperation", "Participation is optional, but strongly recommended", "This survey has no correct/incorrect responses", and "Any data gleaned through this research will be maintained in strict confidence". Second, the cover page comprised the instruction: "Your consent is implied by your agreement to complete this questionnaire." Concerning multilevel modeling, previous literature (Ju et al., 2019; Otake-Ebede et al., 2020) suggests that group-level aggregates of individuals' perception ratings attenuate the problem of CMV. That notwithstanding, a single-factor model was estimated during the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). The results indicated that this model had the worst fit to the data ($\Delta\chi^2 [6] = 1946.01, p < 0.001, \chi^2/df = 11.339, CFI = 0.635, TLI = 0.574, SRMR = 0.161, RMSEA = 0.167$) compared to the hypothesized four-factor model (see below). A poor fitting single factor model suggests that the measured constructs are distinct from each other (discriminant validity), which can be impaired if CMV exists. Moreover, as indicated below, the confidence intervals of the constructs' bivariate correlations did not equate 0.85, which could have been symptomatic of CMV induced discriminant validity concerns. Thus, these findings attenuated the CMV concerns.

Results

4.1 Measurement models

A series of CFAs were performed to assess the measurement model's psychometric properties and factorial validity. First, the hypothesized four-factor model of employee-rated GOS, GTR, GWE, and PEB indicated an adequate fit to the data: $\chi^2/df = 2.439, CFI = 0.951, TLI = 0.941, SRMR = 0.055, RMSEA = 0.062$. Compared to it, a three-factor model with GOS and PEB combined ($\Delta\chi^2 [3] = 744.67, p < 0.001, \chi^2/df = 5.884, CFI = 0.830, TLI = 0.799, SRMR = 0.161, RMSEA = 0.115$) had a worse fit to the data. Furthermore, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) of each latent factor exceeded the threshold of 0.5, and scrutiny of the standardized factor loadings (ranging from 0.61 to 0.912, $p < 0.001$) indicated that each item loaded significantly onto their respective latent factor. As indicated in Table 1, the square roots of the AVEs were greater than each bivariate correlation, and all the correlations and their respective 95% confidence interval did neither straddle one nor equate 0.85 (highest correlation: $r = 0.561, p < 0.001, CI [0.487, 0.627]$) which is considered as a conservative limit (Kline, 2011). Lastly, the composite reliability (ρ_c) and omega (ω) coefficients were used as construct reliability metrics, given the extensively documented shortcomings of the Cronach alpha in the literature (e.g. Goodboy et al., 2020). Each construct's reliability ρ_c and ω coefficients exceeded the recommended threshold (0.7) (see Table 2). These provided substantial support for factorial validity and reliability. A summary of the descriptive statistics and correlations is found in Table 2.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics, correlations, and validity test.

	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. GOS	2.82	1.09	0.853						
2. Resilience	2.42	0.98	0.194***	0.751					
3. Green Work Engagement	2.81	1.09	0.338***	0.368***	0.780				
4. PEBs	2.20	1.03	0.255***	0.400***	0.561***	0.775			

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5. Gender	1.62	0.49	0.047	-0.184***	-0.093	-0.160**			
6. Age	1.99	1.03	0.002	-0.035	-0.074	-0.123*	0.011		
7. Org. tenure	2.03	1.03	-0.1400**	-0.102*	-0.163**	-0.012	0.027	0.059	
8. Education	2.47	1.14	0.041	-0.178***	-0.172***	-0.192***	0.147**	0.090	0.045
ρ_c			0.930	0.885	0.924	0.855			
ω			0.933	0.839	0.914	0.852			
AVE			0.728	0.564	0.608	0.600			

Note. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. Bold values on the diagonal are the AVEs square roots

4.2 Hypotheses testing

Before testing the hypotheses, it is run two separate analyses of variance with random effect ('null models') to assess between-group variance regarding green work engagement and pro-environmental behavior, respectively. For pro-environmental behavior, the null model had a better fit ($\chi^2 [1] = 10.7, p < 0.001$) than the equivalent linear model without a hierarchical structure. The ICC [1] was 0.145, suggesting that employee workgroup accounts for 14.5% of their pro-environmental behavior. For green work engagement, too, the null model fitted better ($\chi^2 [1] = 69.1, p < 0.001$) than the alternative simple linear regression model, and the ICC [1] indicated that group level accounted for 34.7% of the variance in individual green work engagement. These results comforted the use of HLM. For parsimony concern, only the multilevel models of green work engagement and pro-environmental behavior as criterion variables with main cross-level effects were reported (Table 3), which respectively exhibited the best fit compared to the null models and the models with control variables (gender, age, education, and organizational tenure).

Hypothesis 1 suggested that green organizational support is positively related to the green team resilience (H1a), green work engagement (H1b) and, PEB (H3c) of hotel service employees. An ordinary least square regression was employed to test hypothesis H1a proposing a positive association between GOS and GTR since these variables were aggregated at the group level. The results showed that GOS positively and significantly related to GTR ($b = 0.174, p < .001, 95\% \text{ CI } [0.084, 0.264], \eta^2 = 0.245$), thereby supporting H1a. As displayed in Table 2, GOS had a positive association with GWE (Model 1: $\gamma = .409, p < .001, 95\% \text{ CI } [0.258, 0.560]$) and PEB (Model 2: $\gamma = 0.281, p < 0.001, 95\% \text{ CI } [0.178, 0.384]$), which supported hypotheses H1b and H1c.

Table 3. HLM results

	Green work engagement (GWE)		Pro-environmental behaviour (PEB)	
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	
Gender	-0.194* (0.097)	-0.309** (0.103)	-0.163 (0.085)	
Age	-0.040 (0.047)	-0.105* (0.049)	-0.084* (0.04)	
Organizational tenure	-0.092	0.037	0.076	

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	(0.047)	(0.049)	(0.04)
Education	-0.127** (0.043)	-0.144** (0.045)	-0.056 (0.037)
Green organizational support (GOS)	0.409*** (0.077)	0.281*** (0.053)	0.064 (0.058)
Green team resilience (GTR)			0.206*** (0.047)
Green work engagement (GWE)			0.437*** (0.044)
Constant	3.706*** (0.189)	3.207*** (0.253)	2.615*** (0.201)
ICC	0.252	0.088	0.087
R ² marginal	0.197	0.143	0.384
R ² conditional	0.464	0.219	0.491
AIC	1010.987	1028.956	890.963
BIC	1072.491	1083.669	972.133
-2LL ^a	506.651	518.159	450.553

Note. Standard errors are in parentheses. N employees/workgroups = 372/59

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ ^a The deviance of the GWE' null' model was $-2LL = 529.569$, while for PEB' null' model, it was $-2LL = 533.204$. the smaller the deviance, the better the model fit. For Hypothesis 2 and 3, the results show that GWE (H2) and GTR (H3) are also positively associated with hotel employees' PEB. Model 3 also shows that GWE ($\gamma = .437$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [0.35, 0.52]) and GTR ($\gamma = .206$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [0.114, 0.299]) positively related to PEB, which respectively provided support for hypotheses H2 and H3. Hypothesis 4 and 5 state that GTR and GWE mediate the relationship between GOS and PEB. The indirect relationship between GOS and PEB through GTR (H4) was $ab = 0.036$, 95% CI_{MC} [0.014, 0.063], $v^2 = 0.001$, while the indirect relationship between GOS and PEB through GWE (H5) was $ab = 0.127$, 95% CI_{MC} [0.053, 0.219], $v^2 = 0.016$. Although both indirect effects were statistically significant, their effect size (v^2) were respectively 'none' and 'small.' However, Gaskin et al. (2023) suggested that if the effect size is less than the small effect threshold ($v^2 < 0.01$), the related hypothesis may be supported if $n < 400$. Since the study meets these conditions, H4 and H5 were both supported.

5. Discussion

The three main objectives of this research were (a) to assess the role of green organizational support (GOS) as a predictor of green team resilience (GTR), green work engagement (GTR), and pro environmental behavior (PEB) in tourism employees, (b) to assess both the role of GTR and GWE as a predictor of PEB in tourism employees and (c) to test for a intervening role of both GTR and GWE on the relationship between GOS as well as PEB. The present research empirical outcomes substantiate a link between GOS and GTR at the departmental level within

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the hotel industry. This implies that supervisors' theoretical backing and promotion of eco-friendly initiatives within their immediate work groups significantly contribute to the resilience of these hotel departments against environmental challenges. This finding aligns with Fredrickson's (2001) Broaden-and-Build theory, which posits that acknowledging and fostering a pleasant and supportive work environment cultivates cohesive behavior and attitudes among team members. The supportive environment created by GOS enables employees to broaden their thought-action repertoires and build enduring personal and social resources, enhancing their resilience. Our results extend prior empirical evidence within the hotel industry, reinforcing the idea that organizational or leadership support for eco-friendly initiatives positively impacts employees' resilience (Çop et al., 2021). By focusing on the departmental level, this study highlights the crucial role of immediate supervisors in shaping and fostering GTR through the promotion of environmental sustainability practices. This contribution is particularly significant as it addresses a gap in the literature where most studies have concentrated on individual-level or consumer perspectives rather than on employees' direct experiences and behaviours (Arici & Uysal, 2022). Moreover, findings indicate a positive correlation between GOS and GWE at the department level. This relationship is significant as it aligns with the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) framework by Demerouti et al. (2001), which posits that the availability of resources in the workplace serves as a motivational factor that enhances employee engagement. Specifically, the JD-R framework suggests that when employees perceive strong organizational support for eco-friendly initiatives, they are more likely to engage in environmentally responsible behaviors. This theoretical perspective provides a robust foundation for understanding how GOS can influence employee behavior in addressing environmental challenges. Our research findings corroborate previous studies by Darban et al. (2022) and Aboramadan (2022), which demonstrate that eco-friendly practices within hotels stimulate environmental engagement among employees. By providing empirical evidence of the link between GOS and GWE, current research adds to the existing literature by highlighting the critical role of departmental-level support in fostering employee engagement in sustainable practices. This is particularly relevant in the hospitality industry, where environmental challenges are pervasive and the role of employees in addressing these challenges is crucial. Furthermore, by adopting a multilevel approach, this study breaks away from the predominant individual-level focus in the extant GOS literature. This methodological advancement is grounded in both theoretical and statistical robustness, responding to recent calls in the field for more nuanced practices, particularly within nested structures (Tanova & Bayighomog, 2022). By examining GOS and GWE at the department level, this study provides fresh insights into how organizational support can permeate through different levels of the organization, thereby enhancing the overall effectiveness of environmental sustainability initiatives. Following social exchange theory (SET) principles (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005), organizations demonstrating a commitment to the environment by engaging in explicit eco-friendly activities, offering green support, and supervising eco-friendly development are likely to prompt reciprocal green behaviours among employees. The current findings align with prior research by Aboramadan (2022) and Karatepe et al. (2022), elucidating the influence of engaged employees on PEB. Moreover, our results corroborate the positive association between GWE and PEB, affirming Hypothesis 2. This suggests that individuals with higher GWE levels tend to engage in trustworthy and high-quality interactions with

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their organization, fostering a conducive environment for employees to exhibit ecofriendly behaviour. These findings further validate earlier research demonstrating GWE's stimulation of green work outcomes among hotel employees (Darban et al., 2022; Karatepe et al., 2022). The relationship between GTR and PEB can be further understood through the lens of the broaden-and-build theory, which posits that positive emotions broaden individuals' thought-action repertoires and build their enduring personal resources. Previous empirical evidence has indicated that employee resilience is a precursor to positive job outcomes (Hartmann et al., 2020) and that resilient employees are more prone to engage in extra-role performance (Jung & Yoon, 2015). In resilient teams, the positive emotional climate fostered by collective resilience leads to an expanded capacity for creative problem-solving and innovative thinking. This broadened perspective encourages employees to explore and engage in a wider range of pro-environmental behaviors. Additionally, as these positive experiences accumulate, they build durable resources, such as a stronger commitment to environmental values and an enhanced sense of collective efficacy (Malik & Singh, 2024). These resources, in turn, reinforce individual motivation to engage in PEB, as employees feel more empowered and supported to act in environmentally responsible ways. Thus, GTR not only helps teams navigate challenges but also cultivates an environment where pro-environmental behaviors can thrive, driven by the positive emotions and resources generated through resilience. The aforementioned rationale is in line with the theory of broaden-and-build theory because the theory suggests that positive emotions broaden an individual's awareness and encourage novel, varied, and exploratory thoughts and actions (Fredrickson, 2001). In addition, our research investigated the mediating role of GTR in the relationship between GOS and PEB using the job demands-resources (JD-R) paradigm. The findings reveal that job resources, in the form of GOS, significantly enhance GTR, which in turn increases employees' propensity to engage in PEB. This relationship highlights a crucial pathway through which organizational support for environmental initiatives fosters resilience within teams, thereby promoting sustainable behaviors among employees. The JD-R paradigm suggests that job resources not only directly contribute to positive outcomes but also buffer against job demands, thus enabling employees to thrive even in challenging environments. In this context, GOS acts as a valuable resource by providing the necessary support, tools, and motivation for employees to develop resilience within their teams. This resilience, or GTR, serves as a psychological and functional buffer that empowers teams to remain committed to environmental goals despite potential setbacks or challenges. Anchored in the JD-R theory, which posits that job resources foster employee engagement leading to positive work-related outcomes (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017), present research delineates the GOS → GWE → PEB pathway. This analysis confirms earlier research suggesting GWE as a foundational mechanism in the relationship between green-related job resources (GOS) and eco-friendly job outcomes (PEB) (Darban et al., 2022; Karatepe et al., 2022). Following the JD-R paradigm, findings highlight that job resources (GOS) bolster GTR and subsequently elevate employees' propensity toward PEB. These results, supplemented by limited existing research (Meneghel et al., 2016), underscore the influential role of GOS in shaping green behaviors and outcomes among employees in the tourism domain.

Conclusions and implications

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6.1 Theoretical implications

Our study adds to the literature regarding eco-friendly workplace behaviour as well as its consequences, directed by a theoretical model under the umbrella of the broaden-and-build theory (Fredrickson, 2001), social exchange theory (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005), and the job demands-resources (JD-R) theory (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017). The aforementioned theoretical foundations not only guide the development of hypotheses but also facilitate the exploration of the intricate relationships between green supervisor support (GOS), green team resilience (GTR), green work engagement (GWE), and proenvironmental behaviour (PEB). Specifically, this research addresses the call by Bhatnagar and Aggarwal (2020) for further exploration into eco-friendly culture within workplace. It aims to fill the research lacuna in understanding green organizational support, which has been overlooked in systematic review studies (Arici & Uysal, 2022; Tang et al., 2023; Zaidi & Azmi, 2024). Broadly speaking, the first contribution of this multilevel study is evidence of the effects of green organizational support (GOS) among hotel employees. GOS is a crucial employment resource that raises hotel employees' environmental consciousness and provides sufficient training and assistance to become more eco-friendly followers. In addition, the relevant study provides scant evidence about the impact of GOS on eco-friendly job outcomes (Aboramadan & Karatepe, 2021). This research investigates the relationship between GOS, GTR, GWE, and PEB in light of these observations. These findings are essential to the literature because neither meta-analysis nor systematic literature review work has reported linkages above (Tanova & Bayighomog, 2022; Paulet et al., 2021). Secondly, the aforementioned systematic review, as well as meta-analysis, have not revealed any proof of the mediators of green supervisor support. The current study expands the understanding of the GOSPEB relationship through the mediating role of GTR. It seems that our paper is the first that has gauged the intervening role of GTR in the link between GOS and PEB effects. Broadly speaking, the available literature appears to need more findings on the mechanism between GOS and eco-friendly job outcomes (Aboramadan & Karatepe, 2021). More importantly, the studies lack information about the mechanism by which GOS is associated with work consequences (Ari et al., 2020). This paper fills this research lacuna by scrutinizing the role of GTR as a mediator of the effect of GOS on PEB (Kim et al., 2019). Lastly, this study is the testing of GWE as a mediator between GOS and PEB. This is essential given the paucity of research on the mediating mechanism between GOS and eco-friendly job outcomes, particularly in the tourism sector (e.g., Aboramadan et al., 2021; Darban et al., 2022).

6.2 Practical implications

The findings from this research hold significant implications for managerial practices within the hotel sector. First, managers should enhance employees' perception of green organizational support (GOS) and view it as a means to harness their potential for generating creative solutions to environmental challenges. Our research indicates that managers should bolster their employees' environmental initiatives by cultivating their green skills and motivation, and by offering opportunities to develop a sense of GOS. When employees feel supported by management, they are more likely to engage in innovative behavior's aimed at achieving environmental objectives (Hameed et al., 2022). Second, the administration of hotels should boost the exposure of eco-friendly activities and efforts for environmental sustainability. This is possible via the hotel's official website and social media

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platforms such as Instagram and Facebook. Relevant actors would view that the organization invests in greening the workplace, recognizes the importance of the human element in green hotel management, assists employees in addressing various environmental issues, and honours employee contributions to sustainability (Karatepe et al., 2022). Third, to improve green work engagement in a contemporary work sphere, managers should employ sustainability in daily operations utilizing innovative lines. Hotel management also could utilize digital platforms for clear communication of environmental objectives as well as progress. In addition, fostering engagement via virtual team-building activities, remote collaboration projects, and gamified challenges that reward sustainable practices. Recognizing and celebrating sustainability achievements via social media and internal channels to encourage wider participation could be another way to hearten employees' endeavors toward sustainable practices. Moreover, offering flexible work arrangements to reduce the carbon footprint and support work-life balance might be useful. Providing continuous education on cutting-edge environmental practices through webinars and online courses is another strategy to engage employees to eco-friendly activities. By embedding eco-friendly activities into the modern work culture, managers can inspire a sustained commitment to environmental stewardship. Lastly, hotel management can bolster green team resilience (GTR) by fostering a supportive and collaborative work environment centred on environmental initiatives. Encouraging teamwork, providing avenues for open communication, and nurturing a culture that values innovative problem-solving approaches to environmental challenges are instrumental in cultivating GTR. Management should prioritize team-building activities focused on environmental sustainability, recognizing and rewarding collective efforts that showcase resilience in facing ecological adversities. Empowering teams to navigate and adapt to changing environmental landscapes while emphasizing the significance of collaborative efforts can fortify GTR within hotel workgroups.

6.3 Limitations and future research

Despite these advantages, it is essential to recognize the limitations of this research. First, it is assessed the study hypotheses using self-report data at a single time point. Although CMV concern was reduced using administrative and statistical methods, including multilevel modelling, future research must acquire time-lagged data and/or supervisor evaluations for workplace outcome variables and temporal separation between employee-level variables. Second, to mitigate potential self-report biases, future research could benefit from using multiple data sources, such as peer or supervisor evaluations, or incorporating objective measures like energy usage or waste reduction metrics, to complement self-reported data on pro-environmental behavior. Additionally, potential biases such as response styles or the impact of individual differences on self-reports should be considered, as they may influence the accuracy of the data. Future research could explore these factors further by employing techniques such as response pattern analysis or controlling for individual differences in the analysis. Third, conducting cross-national studies could offer insights into how cultural and regional differences affect the relationship between GOS and workplace outcomes. Moreover, investigating specific interventions or strategies to enhance GOS and its impact on workplace outcomes could provide practical insights for organizations. Fourth, the positive workplace performance outcomes employed in this study were PEB. Non-green outcomes can likewise be utilized

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as an outcome variable of GOS. Future studies should also incorporate other organization-level constructs like the green organizational culture and processes at the hotel level that apply to all departments and all workers within each department utilizing a trickledown paradigm and extend this research model with more team or organizational-level control variables. Lastly, based on our findings, future research could explore the effects of GOS in different hotel contexts, such as luxury versus budget accommodations, to determine whether the impact of GOS varies across different operational environments. Additionally, conducting longitudinal studies would be valuable in assessing the long-term impact of GOS on employee behavior's, providing insights into how sustained organizational support influences pro-environmental actions over time

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